

iCanRobots—Active, Holistic, and Inclusive STEAM Education that Empowers Communities

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Abstract

The Global Fab City Initiative’s Full Stack model has six interconnected operative layers that provide a vision for self-sustained urban economies. Layer five calls for “New forms of learning.” Instead of searching for an unspecified “New,” we propose an instructional design approach to education that utilizes teaching and learning methods based on their Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs). To begin, we demonstrate the feasibility of active and holistic STEAM education with the course “Ich kann autonome Roboter!” (“I can do autonomous robotics!” or iCanRobots for short). Instructional methods include a think-pair-share schedule of inquiry-based activities (free play and systematic exploration) and accumulate into individual portfolios.

Next, we go meta and situate iCanRobots in the Design-Based Research (DBR) approach to education and make explicit the connections of teaching and learning methods to ILOs. We developed iCanRobots around instructional design goals of the “I can” format. With iCanRobots, we illustrate how learning activities foster self-development and collaboration skills. It is a prototype course for transdisciplinary education that is empowering and inclusive.

We conclude with a vision for participative and empowering education. Integrative instructional designs provide viable pathways towards active, fun, and inclusive approaches to STEAM in Fab Labs worldwide

Keywords

inquiry-based activities, think-pair-share, empowering education, holistic STEAM approach, FabLabs in communities

1 Introduction

The Global Fab City Initiative proposes the Full Stack model as a “framework across multiple scales of the global urban context” (Full Stack Caption from the blog.fab.city by Fab City Global Initiative, 2019). It is a six-layer model for achieving local production carried out by fab labs worldwide and facilitated by synergies. Layers one to four describe four different paths to realize global connectivity among local and distributed operations. Its bottom two layers operate rather locally and address Fab Labs’ contributions to education and integration in local communities. Our focus is on layer five:

New forms of learning: New skills to learn how to learn, learning by doing principles, lifelong learning basis. The Academy of Almost Anything (Fab Academy, Bio Academy, Fabricademy), STEAM education and professional training. (ibid., p. 1).

While we could not agree more with the specific goals—in which we read holistic, active, and inclusive education—as the fundamental for empowering individuals and communities, we challenge the search for New. Our concern is that looking for some magical New might obscure the magic happening in formal and informal learning environments at fab labs and academies worldwide.

Note that we don't pitch New vs. Old because we consider a novel vs. established distinction an irrelevant classifier for a learning environment. Instead, we suggest utilizing the fab educators' motivations and goals as driving forces to iteratively improving teaching and learning. To that end, we apply the methodology of Design-Based Research (DBR) to education. DBR is a relatively recent educational research trend, advanced among others by Bakker (2018), Reinmann (2020), Pool and Laubscher (2016), Sandoval (2014). In response to the Full Stack and Fab Education, three DBR features are worth pointing out:

- **Goal-Driven:** Innovation is anchored, evaluated, and improved concerning specific goals.
- **Iterative:** No design is perfect, and DBR approaches are inherently iterative—including prototyping, evaluating, and improving educational environments and practices.
- **Going Meta:** By phrasing one's goals and processes explicitly, educators can exchange ideas and, thus, facilitate the iterative improvement of teaching and learning environments. DBR proponents (quite prominently, Reinmann (2020), Sandoval (2014)) stress the importance of concurrent advancement of educational practices and consolidating theoretical insights.

We introduce DBR after, firstly, demonstrating the feasibility of active, inclusive, and holistic STEAM education with the course "Ich kann autonome Roboter!". The course name translates to "I can do autonomous robotics!" and from now on, abbreviated as iCanRobots. Secondly, we describe the educational methodologies of our instructional design with a DBR model. Finally, we conclude with a vision for participative and empowering education integrated into the communities within the FabCity framework.

2 iCanRobots: A Prototype Course for STEAM Education

2.1 Inspiration and Planning

The educational technology is inspired by the work of Dr. Christian Faubel, an electrical engineer and media artist who has conducted over 50 workshops internationally. The children build robots that are imaginative artworks and dance in bright light. They autonomously form exciting constellations. In the same way, the robot costumes have a visual aesthetic and invite acting. Dr. Evelina Dineva is a scholar in mathematics, cognitive neuroscience, and educational research. She explores the basic mechanisms of learning as an embodied cognitive process. In addition, she develops teaching and learning environments with a holistic approach to inquiry-based learning. For the iCanRobots, Kathia von Roth joined the instructor team. Her academic degree is in theater directing, and she brings a unique perspective on functions and usage of (public) spaces, "combining methods of theatrical play and performance with tools and theory of (analogue) game design and software design" (Kathia's webpage). Evelina, Christian, and other colleagues created a neuroscience curriculum for 6th graders (Dineva et al., 2011, unpublished grant proposal). In addition, we contributed to graduate student workshops using autonomous robotics towards theoretical neuroscience (Schöner et al., 2016). Based on our experiences in academia, we believe that autonomous robotics lends itself to a holistic approach to the transdisciplinary field of neuroscience because the connected parts create emergent behavior. When working on autonomous robotics from many perspectives, one is practicing flexible focus control. Repeatedly, one is keeping and shifting the focus between parts' and system's functions. Assuming and releasing views can create an understating of parts and systems, their coupling, and emergent functionalities. To put it bolder, we insert that a multi-perspective approach is a prerequisite to any holistic (STEAM) education.

Holistic STEAM Education

iCanRobots is a starkly reduced version of the 6th-grade neuroscience curriculum that aims to provide holistic STEAM education. Specifically, children build vehicle 1 (Braitenberg, 1986) as solar robots from simple electronic components. They also create cardboard costumes to reenact robots. The underlying concept is described in the course announcement:

I can [do] autonomous robots! We learn how primitive robots generate complex behavior. You solder a Braitenberg vehicle (named after the discoverer) from simple components. Your robot is autonomous, and its behavior is stimulated by light without a computer. Depending on the connection of sensors to motors, it turns away or towards the light. We discover how different circuits work together through systematic play—some call it experimentation because we document everything well. We learn how mechanics and electronics work together to produce behavior. Using an overhead projector (OHP), we enlarge the robots as templates to create costumes. The trick of the costumes is that they limit your senses and behavioral range, just like the robot. In the costume, you experience with your body how robots process information. As a finale, all the children present their robots dancing on the projector as imaginative figures and perform a play with their costumes. (Free-hand transcription of the iCanRobots announcement.)

The neuroscience curriculum mentioned above also reflects our experiences as learners, teachers, and researchers in the transdisciplinary neuroscience field:

1. practice routines—the handy research work and methods—to create some automatism;
2. create opportunity for systematic exploration but also open play;
3. facilitate exchange among students to learn from each other’s diverse sets of skills;
4. integrate insights by practicing shifting focus between themes and scales;
5. explicit connections by addressing focus shifts on a meta-level;
6. support learning to learn through formative feedback;
7. create space for students to document and demonstrate their achievements and experience empowerment through scholarship.

We mention those experiences explicitly because they provide key instructional design principles, informing the creation of teaching and learning environments. On a meta-level, notice that Hounsell et al. (2005) propose utilizing field-specific Ways of Thinking and Practicing (WTP) as a means to enhancing teaching-learning environments. So our take-home message to all Fab people is: Your Fab tasks and routines may be a valuable WTP worth considering explicitly in your teaching.

Recruiting the Commons

Since **#Fabricating the Commons** is FAB16’s theme, we want to share a Lesson Learned with other FabLab-activist who what to do more than just “preaching to the [STEAM] choir.” Independently, Evelina and Christian have encountered difficulties reaching out to people who are not already STEAM affine. We learned the importance of joining forces with local organizations, who work with minority or disadvantaged communities from failing to recruit diverse participants. They know how to reach out and can mediate because people trust them. Consequently, we organized the iCanRobots course with Jürgen Havlik from the Alles Wird Schön (AWS) gallery, a non-commercial neighborhood association. Jürgen is AWS’s executive council and has experience with providing outreach programs for kids, youth, and adults. AWS offers affordable art, music, and media programs in Heimfeld, a quite international and relatively poor neighborhood in Hamburg. Jürgen’s experiences were essential in recurring participants who represent the diverse population in Heimfeld. Thus, we could bring valuable STEAM learning experiences to the commons in a traditionally underserved community by joining forces.

2.2 Conducting iCanRobots

In March 2020, we conducted the course over five days. Twenty-four children (age between six and fourteen years) participated in two groups: twelve participants, two instructors, and two assistants. In addition, children under the age of eight were accompanied by a parent or older sibling. Table 1 shows the daily schedule. Note that we organized a free lunch, to which all participants, instructors, assistants, and accompanying family were invited. Thereby, groups of about five participating children took turns helping the cook prepare lunch, set up tables, and clean afterward. Together, we lunched in a Children’s Club about 40 m from the course venue, the Alles Wird Schön gallery. Nearby are also two backyards with playgrounds, where children can pass brakes.

time event	venue
9 AM—12 PM morning course	Alles Wird Schön
12 PM—2 PM cooking and eating together	Children's Club
2 PM—5 PM afternoon course	Alles Wird Schön

Table 1: iCanRobots daily schedule for Monday till Friday, March 2.–6, 2020.

Both courses were virtually identical curricula, but we adjusted times and tasks as needed. Since this was a voluntary class during the school spring break, we permitted sufficient flexibility to adapt to the children's interests, levels, and needs. Without addressing the individual adaptations in detail, few extra-curricula examples include playground breaks or tracing OHP images of the surrounding/outside. The collage series (Figures 1–4) and course schedules by day (Tables 2–4) document the learning activities. Also, a course trailer is on the course project website.¹

2.3 Instructional Design Elements

Inquiry-based learning with a focus on acquired competencies is the overarching concept for iCanRobots. We developed the learning activities that stimulate creative [2.3, 2.4, 4.1] and scientific practices [1.7, 2.5, 2.6, 4.3] (IDs according to Tables 2–4). Those activities are at the core of inquiry-based learning and, in concert, geared to facilitating learning by placing children's achievements in the foreground to themselves, their peers, and larger audiences. Specifically, we applied educational methodologies that foster competence acquisition, including learning to learn. Specific instructional design elements are geared to create active, holistic, and inclusive instruction into STEAM disciplines:

1. inquiry-based learning through free play and systematic exploration;
2. think-pair-share (TPS) schedule of activities that enhances self-development and collaboration; and
3. individual portfolio and final presentation to consolidate learning outcomes.

Think-Pair-Share Schedule

We like to stress the TPS method because we believe it is a crucial instructional design element for learning to learn. Specifically, TPS fosters generic competencies like self-competencies, collaborative working, and scientific communication.

- **Think** Each child gains perspective on autonomous robotics (circuits, functions, stimulus-response) through individual work and crafts.
- **Pair** In pairs, children exchange ideas with each other in a familiar environment. They consolidate thereby what they learned and practice formulating thoughts, assessing themselves, and cooperating.
- **Share** They prepare to share their findings independently in the large group. Finally, the children present their work, knowledge, and skills to the outside world.

TPS is also an inclusive teaching method because it gives students time to think about an issue independently before sharing it with their peers. And sharing with peers allows students to formulate their thoughts and learn from one another before presenting ideas publicly. People are different and express their knowledge or skills in different ways. By enabling multiple communication channels, more options for finding one's mode of expression exists. During the Pair and Share phases, students read, hear, and see different styles. Pairing students with varying skill levels has the additional advantage that the more advanced student is practicing their knowledge while gaining experience teaching.

¹ <https://alles-wird-schoen-e-v.de/portfolio-items/culture-dialogue> (last retrieved on July 28, 2021)

Empowering Experiences

On the final day, we invited friends and family to the iCanRobots presentation. We see this as a crucial “I can!”-format for empowering students because their work is recognized by others and relived by the students.

You Can [Do Robots]! The instructors began the ceremony by awarding the participating students with a certificate recognizing their achievements during the “I can do autonomous robotics!” course. Namely, they developed competencies to

- solder autonomous robots;
- recognize and name electronic components and recognize their functions;
- understand and explain the function of an electronic circuit;
- understand and explain how a robot can produce behavior;
- understand and explain the difference between autonomous or programmed robotics; • understand and explain stimulus-response connectivity;
- understand and explain relationships of projections and scaling transformation;
- extract mathematical relationships about scaling;
- work collaboratively in pairs and small groups;
- explain one’s results in the whole class;
- present results and achievements to an external audience.

Moreover, students received a decorative certificate for display and a set of pictures recording their activities. They also kept all artifacts from their work during the class: portfolios, robots, and consumes. The artifacts, records, and certificates have the primary purpose of letting the children become aware (and proud) of their achievements. Their additional purpose is the consolidation of results, helping to recall learning experiences and thereby deepening memory.

I Can [Do Robots]! The children concluded the course by presenting their artifacts, photos, and portfolios to their family and friends—in a safe space. The presentation in front of an audience also serves multiple educational goals. Primary, children experience and communicate their work. They are becoming aware of and awarded for their achievements. Experiencing one’s progress is, we believe, essential to learning to learn.

3 Going Meta: DBR Approach/es to Education

3.1 Why DBR?

Above, we describe the iCanRobots course without presenting data/results because our research is NOT a pseudo-/experimental study (the most frequent empirical method in educational research, mainly used to evaluate novel approaches to teaching and learning). On one hand, we believe that pseudo-/experiment are not suited in many teaching and learning scenarios because an experimental evaluation requires well-defined, scandalized, and peer-approved measuring tools. More often than not, a pseudo-/experiment in education uses ad-hock evaluations tools. In addition, most of those are too specific to be replaceable.

On the other hand, if an experiment is well designed and uses a scandalized tool, then the stickily controlled experiment is doomed to be very specific, and results are not very useful in practice. Put simply: Education is too messy for strict data. Moreover, especially on the relatively small scale of Fab Labs, many factors co-vary with every course/method/event.

Instead of forcing evidence-based research that compares a single method over some presumed standard, we were inspired to see that educational research has more to offer. Specifically, Design-Based Research (DBR) is a methodology revolving (pun intended) around specific design goals. According to Bakker (2018), the premise is simple: educational researchers and practitioners improve education for one of two reasons. Namely, they want to solve a problem or have an idea of improving education. Thus, in contrast to a pre/post-test where something novel N is compared to a standard control condition C , DBR does not ask if N is **better than** C . Instead, DBR is concerned with **how to** make education better.

3.2 What is DBR?

There is excellent literature addressing this question, for instance, Bakker (2018), Reinmann (2020), Pool and Laubscher (2016), Sandoval (2014). However, for the scope of this paper, it suffices to say that DBR is bringing the design process of educational environments to the forefront of research. In the words of Prpic and Hadgraft (2011, p. 156):

In contrast to laboratory experimental research, DBR is applicable where multiple variables are involved, where the control of those variables is difficult or unlikely and where quantitation is difficult or even illusory. Nevertheless, the aim of DBR is to provide a body of evidence in support of theory. Despite its similarity to many engineering design processes, DBR has not as yet been widely used in engineering education research.

We believe that DBR is a viable approach to education in Fab Labs for the very same reasons. Also, like for engineering, design practices and iterations are common in Fab Labs. Therefore, we anticipate DBR thinking to be easily accessible and appreciated.

3.3 How to DBR?

Disclosure: Our iCanRobots research is not a full-blown DBR study because we did not evaluate educational goals, learning activities, or instructional design elements (Sections 2.1–2.3). At the time of the course, we wanted to provide the experiences and realized only later the value of our course design. iCanRobots is a feasible prototype that needs further testing and iterations—a first DBR iteration.

Most DBR researchers work with models. An accessible model for DBR, we find, is the Conjecture Mapping by Sandoval (2014, p. 22, p. 24): “I use the term conjecture here to connote the usually highly provisional nature of the ideas we have about how to design a learning environment at the start of a design research project.” The so-called “Design conjectures take the general form ‘if learners engage in this activity (task + participant) structure with these tools, through this discursive practice, then this mediating process will emerge.’” This level of granularity is what we aimed for with the description of iCanRobots in Section 2. Strictly speaking, our design conjectures are very rudimentary but a first step towards making instructional design explicit.

Reinmann (2020, p. 3) proposes the holistic DBR model with five Semantic Fields “[Iteration Type I] goal setting, conception, development, testing, and analysis.” The model is holistic because it acknowledges that researchers do and iterate all those Semantic Fields during a design process. Moreover, they shift focus between the Fields and their whole and or combinations of neighboring Fields. We mention the holistic model here because it focuses on what educational DBR researchers do, and thus, it might be close to design practices in Fab Labs.

4 Outlook

With iCanRobots, we illustrate how a “hands-on” to “minds-on” approach empowers learners, which is the core idea of the “I can [substitute with your favorite topic]” format. Albeit it was a hell of a lot of work to do the iCanRobots course, we also had fun doing it. And we are happy about the positive resonance from the kids and parents. Unfortunately, we did not measure intended learning outcomes nor student satisfaction. However, many moments during the class felt successful respective our initial goals: holistic STEAM, inclusive, and empowering. Thus, we hope that our prototype course will provide a blueprint for

using teaching and learning strategies to formulate and achieve Fab education. Note that advancing education in the iCanRobots case takes place at different scales beyond teaching:

- Developing a holistic STEAM concept
- Planning of activities
- Recruitment in the community
- Conducting the course

Thus, the instructional design also happens on diverse scales.

We also claim that iteratively improving education is more potent than searching for new, better teaching methods. To that end, we introduce the DBR approach, which provides an iterative process for continually improving teaching and learning environments. Bringing a meta-level perspective to education is powerful because it allows for a language framework for peer exchange, from which synergies may emerge. Synergies bring us back to the Full Stack model, but now to level three:

Shared Strategies Adapted to local needs Global programs for urban transformation related to local production and processing of food, energy, water, information, or other production systems. Implementation and deployment strategies by the Fab City Collective. Fab City Prototypes. (Fab City Global Initiative, 2019, p 1)

Just like for urban transformation for goods and energies, a theoretical approach to education will permit intellectual cross-pollination.

In conclusion, we believe that we share the design goals—holistic STEAM, inclusive, and empowering education—with the Fab community and hope that our prototype course will provide a blueprint on how to keep improving education.

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Appendix: Course Materials and Documentation

The attached Tables 2–4 list the activity schedules per day. Those are followed by a collage series depicting the learning activities. Note that Figures 1–4 are composed thematically (i.e., not chronologically). Finally, we attach the worksheets with formal exercises; those are in the course language, German.

Each activity listed in the tables has an ID, the ID format is day[nr].activity[nr].[tpsi] with the first digit listing the day and activity in chronological order. The initials [tpsi] indicate a think, pair, share, or instructor activity. Whenever applicable, the IDs (just the numbers on a yellow background) point to respective scenes in the course collage in the picture series. We used the wall space to keep important information continually available. Some numbers have an orange background; they point to artifacts that help keep inputs present throughout the course.

Table 2: Activity schedule on Day one.

ID	activity	material	instructor/s	participant/s
1.1.t	introduction	cards, markers, tape, wall space	demonstrates activity before participants repeat	write 3–5 characteristics on a card, use it introduce yourself, and fix the card on the wall
1.2.ps	connecting	rope, cards [1.1]	demonstrates activity before participants repeat	name a connection between one’s own and another card, mark it with a rope
1.3.ps	communication	OHP, foil, markers	asks “How do we want to communicate?” and writes rules on the OHP	discuss the question first with a neighbor, then in group
1.4.i	agreement	foils [1.3], wall space	calls attention and hangs the foils with the communication rules on the wall	listen
1.5.it	electronic parts and circuit	worksheet w/ circuit sketch, robot kit	presents the robot parts and explains their function	sketch the parts on their worksheet and take notes
1.6.p	soldering solar robot	robot kits, soldering tools	supervises and attends as needed	in pairs, one child solders a robot while the other assist holding parts in place
1.7.tpi	debugging and fixing	OHP, voltmeter, solar robot [1.6], worksheet [1.5]	guides testing, debugging, and fixing; e.g., helps to check the circuit and connections	test on the OHP if the robot moves, debug using their circuit worksheets and voltmeter

Table 3: Activity schedule on Day two.

ID	activity	material	instructor/s	participant/s
2.1.p	as [1.6] but with reverse roles in each team			
2.2.tpi	as [1.7] until both robots are moving on an OHP			
open choices: decorating robots [2.3], playing with robots and projections [2.4], and different degrees of guided structured exploitation [2.5, 2.6]				
2.3.tp	decorating robots	light gels, art supplies	minimal supervising and assisting	decorate robots and may pair up as wanted
2.4.tp	projections and robots	OHP, robots	n/a	plying and exploring the peculiar aesthetics of gel-decorated robots and their shadows
2.5.ti	experiment: tracing robot's behavior	OHP (w/ foils), solar robots (aka vehicle 1)	introduces tracing robots overt behavior by attaching a pencil to leave a trace on the foil	reshape the robot (e.g. number or position of legs on an OHP) and observe how movement patterns change
2.6.ti	experiment: measuring	OHP, robots (vehicle 1)	shows how to measure discharge rates of robot (vehicle 1) and introduces firing properties (like a neuron)	use the voltmeter on robot in action on an OHP and protocol the data

Table 4: Activity schedule on Day three.

ID	activity	material	instructor/s	participant/s
3.1psi	space and senses	classroom/outside	explains rules and guides games	interact with one another and explore space with different senses
3.2t	making goggles	cut-out sets, colored translucent paper	supervises and attends as needed	fold goggle flowing instructions and blind-fold those such that only color can shine thru
3.3si	programmed robot	blindfolds/goggles [3.2], audio signals	explains programming following instructions	impersonate a robot, following the programmer's commands
3.4tpi	autonomous robot	sensor cell: translucent goggles [3.2]; stimulus: torch	introduces Braitenberg (1986) vehicles: vehicle 1 (solar robot [1.6]) and 2.a and 2.b (two vehicle 1 connected in parallel or crossed);	impersonate alone vehicle 1 (familiar); in pairs play vehicles 2.a and 2.b; in both cases behavior is simple reaction to a light stimulus that the robot perceives through the goggles

Table 5: Activity schedule on Day four.

ID	activity	material	instructor/s	participant/s
4.1p	tracing projections	robots [2.3], OHP, white cardboard, pencils	supervises and attends as needed	project robot on cardboard to trace it, partner holds the board
4.2ti	imagining projections	space	ask questions projection transformations	answer by moving to assigned places
4.3p	projecting and scaling	transparent rulers and set squares, worksheets, 3 OHPs at different distances from wall	explains exercise/worksheets, then inquires and writes results on an OHP to be visible the wall (regular patterns appear)	each team uses an OHP (at a set distance from wall) to measure how much a ruler (1D) and a set square (2D) is scaled; report results after exercise and search for mathematical relations (recognizable on the wall via an OHP)
4.4si	making robot costume	cardboard w/ traces [4.1], cutter, colors	supervises and attends as needed	creative artworks: decorate robots with color markers, papers, and other art supplies

Table 6: Activity schedule on Day five.

ID	activity	material	instructor/s	participant/s
5.1si	consolidate portfolios	worksheets, folders, foils from wall-repository	recapitulates and assesses previous themes; note: all foils created in course are collected on a wall like the rules agreement [1.3]	answer recap questions, consolidate their worksheets and notes in a portfolio folder
5.2tp	touching up	robots, costumes	supervises and attends as needed	finalize decorations on robots or costumes
5.3s	finale	guests, certificates, printed photos, wall exhibition	award certificates and gives course photos for all students	present the artifacts they created: portfolios, robots, costumes, and wall-art (and keep those afterward)

Figure 1: Different views on and activities with the solar robot (Braitenberg vehicle 1, middle left): Its diagram and components (top left); kids building it (top right) and experimenting with it by tracking the external motion trajectories (bottom right) or recording the internal firing rates (middle right).

Figure 2: Projections exercises using decorated robots and science tools to explore and measure scaling.

Figure 3: Exploring and using space throughout the course: connecting and networking (top) and working (middle) and playing together (bottom). In the play, children experience being autonomous (left) or programmed (right) robots.

Figure 4: Children consolidate their portfolios (top); Everyone is finalizing the artifacts and preparing for the final presentation (bottom); guests attend the final presentation (middle).

Die Schaltung vom Solar-Roboter

Schau dir die Skizze mit der Roboter Schaltung an.
Finde alle Teile und sortiere diese in der Tabelle.

platine	solar	motor
capacitor	fled	r1
t1	t2	r2

Die Teile vom Solar-Roboter

Skizziere die unterschiedlichen Teile und beschreibe, was sie machen oder wie sie funktionieren.

platine

solar

motor

capacitor

fled

r (1, 2)

t (1, 2)

<h3 style="text-align: center;">Aus Klein Mach Gross</h3> <p>Skalieren am OverHead Projektor (OHP): Experimentieren mit Objekten, Entfernungen und Vergrößerungen.</p> <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 33%;">Objekt</th> <th style="width: 33%;">Entfernung</th> <th style="width: 33%;">Vergrößerung</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">	<h2 style="text-align: center;">ZEUGNIS</h2> <h3 style="text-align: center;">ICH KANN AUTONOME ROBOTER!</h3> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Workshop vom 2. bis 6. März 2020</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Hiermit bestätigen wir, dass</i></p> <hr style="width: 20%; margin: 10px auto;"/> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>An Workshop teilgenommen hat und die folgenden Kompetenzen erweitert hat:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - autonome Roboter löten - Bauteile erkennen und benennen und ihre Funktionen verstehen - Grundlagen der Elektronik verstehen - Verständnis darüber, wie ein Roboter nach einfachen Regeln autonomes Verhalten erzeugen kann - Verständnis darüber, wie Projektionen und Skalierung funktionieren - zu Zweit und in Kleingruppen arbeiten - in der Gruppe erklären - die Resultate des Workshop unseren Gästen präsentieren <p style="text-align: center;">ALLES WIRD SCHÖN E.V.</p> <p style="margin-top: 10px;"><i>Hamburg Kleinfield, 6. März 2020</i></p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="text-align: center; font-size: small;">ORT UND DATUM</div> <div style="text-align: center; font-size: small;">WORKSHOPLEITUNG</div> </div>																																																																						
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